

2016 Torino, Italy
CONFERENCE ABSTRACTS

January 22-24, 2016

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wires. three commercial brands of NiTi round wire (Nic-China, Ormco-USA, and Smart-Thailand) with sizes 0.014", 0.016", and 0.018" were studied. Five specimens each size of each brand were used to test mechanical properties: unloading force (N), spring back (mm), and yield strength (N/mm) with three-point bend test using an Instron Universal Testing Machine. Kolmogorov-Smirnov test and one-way ANOVA were employed to test the differences among groups with statistical difference at $p < 0.05$. The average unloading force from lowest to highest were Ormco, Smart and Nic with 0.014", Smart, Ormco and Nic with 0.016" and Smart, Nic and Ormco with 0.018", respectively. The Nic brand had the highest value of unloading force, spring back, and yield strength in all wire sizes, except unloading force 0.018" Ormco and spring back 0.018" Smart. There were no statistically significant differences in unloading forces among all wire sizes. The three brands of commercial orthodontic NiTi wires presented similar unloading force, spring back, and yield strength properties. These mechanical properties are related to lower rates of deformation and are appropriate to be used in the initial phase of orthodontic treatment.

ST0002:

Time:16:45-17:00

The Mathematical Formula Of The Causal Relationship k

Mr Ilija Barukčić

Horandstrasse, DE-26441 Jever, Germany.

The deterministic relationship between cause and effect is deeply connected with our understanding of the physical sciences and their explanatory ambitions. Though progress is being made, the lack of theoretical predictions and experiments in quantum gravity makes it difficult to use empirical evidence to justify a theory of causality at quantum level in normal circumstances, i. e. by predicting the value of a well-confirmed experimental result. For a variety of reasons, the problem of the deterministic relationship between cause and effect is related to basic problems of physics as such. Despite the common belief, it is a remarkable fact that a theory of causality should be consistent with a theory of everything and is because of this linked to problems of a theory of everything. Thus far, solving the problem of causality will help us to solve the problems of the theory of everything (at quantum level).

ST3001:

Time:17:00-17:15

Health Effects of Mobile Tower Radiation on Human – Case Study

Mr Lalrinthara Pachuau, Zaithanzauva Pachuau

Dept. of Physics, Pachhunga University College, Aizawl, Mizoram University, Tanchil, India.

In the present paper, we presented the study of complaints on thirteen (13) different health symptoms faced by inhabitants living near mobile tower – Global System for Mobile Communication (GSM 900 & 1800) and those inhabitants living in the area where there is no mobile tower. The study was conducted in fourteen different localities in Aizawl city and four different localities outside Aizawl city in the year 2014 & 2015. Questionnaires were conducted in all the localities. Power densities were measured in different places in all the localities. Health complaints between the localities were compared with that of the locality where there is no mobile tower. It was found that power density is much higher in the area where there is mobile tower than the area where there is no mobile tower. Questionnaire

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